

PLAN OVERVIEW

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF SMALL ELECTROMAGNETIC HARVESTERS FOR VIBRATIONAL ENERGY SCAVENGING (HAR4BEST)

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Template: Horizon Europe Template

Project abstract:

The HAR4BEST proposal focuses on the development of small electromagnetic vibrational energy harvesters (SEVEHs). These devices collect environmental vibrational energy that, otherwise, will be wasted. Vibrational kinetic energy is harvested from different environmental sources: civil infrastructures (roadways, railways, bridges, buildings), wind and water flow, machine operation in industry, transportation (especially automotive), human motion, among others.

The data management plan (DMP) of the project is being developed taking into account the Open Science practices. The DMP is a living document, which will be updated as required.

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DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF SMALL ELECTROMAGNETIC HARVESTERS FOR VIBRATIONAL ENERGY SCAVENGING (HAR4BEST)

DATA SUMMARY

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

No previous data has been reused.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The project will produce computational tools and experimental data. Computational tools include plain text scripts interpreted by other programs (with extensions .geo .pro .m), problem or geometry definition files (.msh .mph .stl). The experimental data, including experimental procedures and data results, will be properly defined employing open science formats (e.g. Text: TXT; Tabular data: CSV or DAT; Documents: RTF or PDF; Images: PNG; Audio: WAV; Video: MPEG; Compressed data: ZIP; binary hierarchical data: HDF5)

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of the data is designing novel and optimized small vibration energy electromagnetic harvesters, testing the corresponding experimental prototypes, validate the simulations, make this data and software available to other researchers, and publication of the scientific results in JCR high-impact scientific journals. These are fundamental for the project tasks and objectives:

- Development of open-source software for the design of the harvesters
- Optimization of the harvesters
- Development of harvesters for strategic sectors
- Transference of the know-how.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

Generated data has an expected size up to 10 GB. About 50% in raw data (including videos, mesh files, pictures and simulation results), 40% in processed data, and 10% in other data (reports, scripts).

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The data generated are research outputs obtained from experiments and simulations, including raw data, results, negative results, postprocessed data, methods, pictures and software/scripts.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The generated data can be used by other researchers to reproduce and validate the project findings, as well as test their own simulation methods. The shared software and scripts can be used by engineers and product developers to design electromagnetic harvesters, or can be modified for other purposes.

FAIR DATA

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Taking into account the Open Science practices, scientific data will be made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

To make data findable, it will be shared in one or many records or uploads (datasets), each dataset will be provided with a persistent DOI (digital object identifier). In the case of repositories that only provide an url (e.g. github), zenodo will be used to link the dataset to a doi.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Datasets will be provided with the metadata required by the employed repository. In any case, data will be described by normalized metadata standards and vocabularies (e.g. Zenodo uses JSON-schema for rich metadata and can export metadata to other standards such as Dublin Core. Zenodo also uses FAIR or open vocabularies including DataCite's Metadata Schema, Open Definition, FundRef, OpenAIRE).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

In any case, keywords will be provided in the dataset metadata to enhance discovery (as long as the repository allows it, e.g. zenodo allows it).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Repositories that make metadata collectable and indexable (searchable) will be chosen (e.g. Zenodo sends metadata to DataCite servers).

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

This information (whether temporary, permanent, open public, restricted or only available within the research team) will be properly posted making use of public repositories, e.g. topical repositories as GNU Octave Repository or mathworks file exchange repository, and general-purpose repositories as Zenodo, and GitHub, Figshare, Mendeley, The Dataverse project or Dryad as well. Trusted repositories will be preferred.

UPNA institutional repository (academica-e, <https://academica-e.unavarra.es/>) will be employed to share preprints compatible with the particular editorial requirements as well as open access papers. In fact, this institutional repository of UPNA uses national and international standards for the documents descriptors and complies with the interoperability protocol OAI-PMH (Open Access Initiative-Protocol for Metadata Harvesting). It is also collected by OPEN Aire (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe), meeting all its requirements and directives.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Considered repositories are free to use, specifically, academica-e is the institutional repository managed by the University of the Principal Investigators.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Chosen repositories can assign an identifier, but not all of them assign a DOI (e.g. Zenodo provides a doi, github can use a doi created by zenodo, but academica-e assigns a specific url identifier).

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.

Provided no restriction linked to their exploitation and intellectual property potential, generated data will be analyzed and selected to be available in open repositories. Publication of papers in scientific journals will be made in Open Access. The results file of certain FEA (Finite Element Analysis) simulations, which total for TBs of storage space, won't be shared publicly given the required storage capacity and that the file is not needed once postprocessed (graphs and point data obtained postprocessing these files will be shared).

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

If an embargo is applied, it will allow enough time for the publication of research findings or to pursue intellectual property protection, such as patents. The embargo period will not exceed 3 months unless the circumstances extend this time span, aligning with the principle that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Data made open will be free and easy to access in their repository. Access to restricted data can be freely asked to the dataset owner (the researcher who uploads the record to the repository) by email or by the messaging tools provided by each repository.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Data requests will be handled on a case by case basis by the dataset owner using email or the messaging tools provided by each repository.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

If the identity of the person accessing the data is relevant, an institutional email address will be required. Since the project does not manage sensitive data, the identity of the persons accessing the data is not recorded.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee, as there is no personal or sensitive data involved.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Metadata will be made openly available based on the repository policy, e.g. zenodo licenses metadata under a public domain dedication (CC0). The metadata will include all necessary information to enable users to access the data, ensuring transparency and facilitating data reuse. If there are any exceptions to this approach, they will be justified with clear reasons, such as confidentiality, security, or legal constraints.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Data will remain available and findable as long as the repositories exist, which is expected to be a long term given the choice of trusted repositories. Metadata can remain available if the data is not, as this information is harvested by search engines, or sent to metadata databases (depends on the repository, zenodo sends the metadata to DataCite servers).

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Documentation required to access or read the data will be included in the datasets, or linked between datasets, as a general rule datasets and folders will contain at least a readme.txt file explaining the data and how to read it and which software (if any) is required. Software will not be included in the datasets, except for the codes, scripts or software made during the project by the researching team.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

To make data interoperable, standardized open formats will be preferred (see previous question about data formats).

2.3. Making data interoperable:

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

The project uses common terms; however, in case of using uncommon ontologies or vocabularies these will be explained in the dataset readme or the published method or appendix.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

Will your data include qualified references^[1] to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

[1]A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Datasets will contain qualified references to other datasets or publications of the project as needed (particularly, methodologies used to obtain a dataset may be explained in detail in a publication, while a dataset may be linked to a particular publication).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

As a general rule datasets and folders will contain at least a readme.txt file with information required to re-use the data files (variable definitions, units of measurement, methodologies, software required), extensive methodologies may be explained in an open access publication which will be linked to the pertinent dataset.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Datasets and publications will be licensed under standard reuse licenses, a Creative Common CC BY license will be preferably selected.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Since the data produced in the project (except any with legal or size restrictions) will be eventually made open in a repository under a reuse license, the datasets will be useable by third parties, partially during the project and especially some time after the end of the project.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The provenance of the data will be documented in the readme files and translated to standard metadata when the repository supports it (when applicable, information about other source datasets, origin organization and place of the data, issue date, kind of data creation/collection method).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Whenever possible, the peer review process will be the main pillar of data quality assurance. The review process for scientific data publication will be used to ensure the quality of the generated data. In addition, review and feedback tools in data repositories will further enhance the peer review process. If this is not possible, the data will be reviewed by the investigators involved in the project.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Since personal/sensitive data or consent form are not necessary in the project, no special data security or ethics are required.

OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Other research outputs include software, physical prototypes and material samples.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Software and other digital outputs are subject to the same FAIR treatment detailed above. Physical research outputs cannot be shared in the same way, and will be stored in the University Department for a few years, the Principal Investigators will consider any access or reuse request of physical items in a case by case basis.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

The cost of making data and other research outputs FAIR is considered negligible or cannot be precisely calculated: Data is available online, while prototypes and material samples are not specially bulky and do not require security (no biological, personal or toxic samples).

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

In the case of the costs of making research outputs FAIR exists, they will be handled by the University and/or the repository sponsors.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The PI Cristina Gomez Polo will be responsible for data management plan (as stated in the project's work plan, task 5.4). Alternative: Eneko Garayo.

Metadata generation (includes uploading/owning the datasets/records in repositories), data generation/collection/analysis can be performed by any member of the team.

External data centers are responsibility of their respective owners: CERN's zenodo, Universidad de Navarra's academica-e, Elsevier journals, AIP Publishing journals.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Data will be preserved as long as the repositories exist, which is expected to be a long term given the choice of trusted repositories. Cost is negligible. Principal Investigators decide what data is kept (see FAIR principles above).

DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

During the course of research activities, the data is stored on researchers laptops and computer hard drives, and backed up frequently to both external storage and cloud storage (the University provides Microsoft's One Drive cloud storage for free to its researchers). Each researcher is responsible for their generated data at this point and must submit the data to the Principal Investigators when asked. The data will be uploaded to long term storage (repositories) as previously detailed. Since personal or sensitive data is not expected, no special data security is required.

ETHICS

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

There are no ethics or legal issues impacting data sharing, at the moment.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No personal data (or consent questionnaires) are required.

OTHER ISSUES

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Data management takes in mind Open Science practices (e.g. FAIR data, open access), as required by the funder.

PLANNED RESEARCH OUTPUTS

JOURNAL ARTICLE - "FAST CALCULATION METHODS FOR THE MAGNETIC FIELD OF PARTICLE LATTICES"

Journal article presenting calculation methods for the magnetic field of magnetic composites (e.g. magnetic nanoparticles embedded in a 3D printed polymer part). Numerical and experimental comparisons are provided.

DATASET - "FAST CALCULATION METHODS FOR THE MAGNETIC FIELD OF PARTICLE LATTICES: DATASETS AND SCRIPTS"

This directory contains the following datasets and scripts: Matlab scripts to analytically calculate the magnetic field of magnets of some basic shapes, as well as the magnetic field of a composite consisting of a lattice of magnetic particles. Experimental data as well as tabular data required to plot curves in csv format. Methods information in the readme.txt files and more information in the associated paper.

JOURNAL ARTICLE - "ELECTROMAGNETIC VIBRATIONAL HARVESTER BASED ON U-SHAPED FERROMAGNETIC CANTILEVER: A NOVEL TWO-MAGNET CONFIGURATION"

Journal article presenting a small ferromagnetic U-shaped cantilever-based electromagnetic vibration energy harvester (composed of the ferromagnetic cantilever, a coil NdFeB and ferrite magnets). Design methodology employs magnetic circuit analysis and Finite Element Method (FEM). Test results are shown, an experimental resonant frequency of 77 Hz was obtained, enabling the subsequent electronic rectification stage. It is possible to tune the resonance frequency from 51 to 77 Hz, keeping constant the induced voltage.

JOURNAL ARTICLE - "OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE OF LOW FREQUENCY VIBRATION ENERGY HARVESTER BASED ON MAGNETIC LEVITATION"

Journal article presenting a novel ultra low frequency electromagnetic vibration energy harvester based on 1 Degree of Freedom magnetic levitation (e.g. composed of ferrite and NdFeB permanent magnets, a coil and a plastic frame). Design method is detailed (based in both analytical equations implemented via script and 3D FEA (Finite Element

Analysis)), tests results of a prototype are shown, experimental resonant frequency is 1.7 Hz. More information and scripts found in associated dataset.

DATASET - "OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE OF LOW FREQUENCY VIBRATION ENERGY HARVESTER BASED ON MAGNETIC LEVITATION: DATASETS AND SCRIPTS"

This directory contains the following datasets and scripts: Matlab scripts to automate the design and optimize a magnetic spring based vibration energy harvester. Experimental data recorded by the datalogger as well as tabular data required to plot curves in csv format. Methods information in the readme.txt files and more information in the associated paper.

PLANNED RESEARCH OUTPUT DETAILS

Title	DOI	Type	Release date	Access level	Repository (ies)	File size	License	Metadata standard	May contain sensitive data?	May contain PII?
HAR4BEST Data Management Plan (DMP)	10.5281/zenodo.14937106	DMP	2025-02-27	Open	Zenodo	-	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Fast calculation methods for the magnetic field of particle lattices	10.1063/5.0253711	Journal article	2025-02-14	Open	None specified	-	CC-BY-NC-4.0	None specified	No	No
Fast calculation methods for the magnetic ... Datasets and scripts	10.5281/zenodo.13930968	Dataset	2024-10-14	Open	Zenodo	1 MB	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Electromagnetic vibrational harvester based on U-s ...	10.1016/j.ecmx.2024.100705	Journal article	2024-09-05	Open	None specified	-	CC-BY-NC-4.0	None specified	No	No
Electromagnetic vibrational harvester based on U-s ... Datasets	10.5281/zenodo.15466037	Dataset	2025-05-19	Open	Zenodo	8 MB	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Optimization procedure of low frequency vibration ...	10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122778	Journal article	2024-04-01	Open	None specified	-	CC-BY-NC-4.0	None specified	No	No
Optimization procedure of low frequency vibration ... datasets and scripts	10.5281/zenodo.8277126	Dataset	2023-08-23	Open	Zenodo	13 MB	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
A Finite Elements Scheme for the Optimization of Vibrational Energy Electromagnetic Harvesters	Not available yet.	Journal article	Expected 2025	Open	None specified	-	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
FEM library for electromagnetic vibrational energy harvesters	https://github.com/Harvester2022/Harvester	GNU Octave Scripts	2025-07-17	Open	Github	1 MB	GPL-3-0	None specified	No	No

U-shape Magnetostrictive Harvester: Design and Experimental Validation	https://academica-e.unavarra.es/handle/2454/52757	Conference short paper	2024-05-07	Open	Academica-e (repository of UPNA)	-	-	None specified	No	No
Design and Optimization of a Compact Rectangular Galfenol-Based ...	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsna.2025.117231	Journal article	2025-12-16	Open	None specified	-	CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0	None specified	No	No
Design and Optimization of a Compact Rectangular Galfenol-Based ... Datasets	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16276314	Dataset	2025-07-21	Open	Zenodo	7 MB	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Reducing the Environmental Impact and Cost of ultra-low frequency Vibrational Energy Harvesters ...	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnconman.2025.121028	Journal article	2026-01-06	Open	None specified	-	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Reducing the Environmental Impact and Cost of ultra-low frequency Vibrational Energy Harvesters ...: Datasets and scripts.	https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16280644	Dataset	2025-07-21	Open	Zenodo	108 MB	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
2DOF VIBRATION LEVITATION-BASED HARVESTER REPORT: DATASET	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16999786	Dataset and white paper	2025-08-31	Open	Zenodo	3 MB	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No